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Supporting Children with Reading Difficulties in Nigeria Using School Based Counseling Strategies

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Abstract: *This paper examined how children with reading difficulties in Nigeria can be supported through school-based counselling strategies. The paper discussed school-based counselling strategies in supporting children with reading difficulties, educational application of school-based strategies that will help in remediating reading difficulties, factors responsible for reading difficulties and how it impacts children's academic progress. Reading difficulties can be characterized by significant and persistent difficulties in reading skills that are substantially below what is expected for a child age and grade level. However, school-based counseling provides a supportive framework through which students can receive emotional, psychological, and academic support tailored to their unique learning needs.*

Key word: School Based counselling, reading difficulties, counseling strategies.

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Introduction

Reading is one of the most essential academic skills that significantly influences a child's overall educational achievement. Unfortunately, many children in Nigeria struggle with reading difficulties, which hinder their ability to learn effectively and perform well in school. Reading difficulties are characterized by persistent difficulties in decoding, comprehension, and fluency, despite having normal intelligence and access to conventional classroom instruction. These challenges, if not properly addressed, often lead to poor academic performance, low self-esteem, and emotional distress among affected children.

Reading difficulties is a process when a child shows significant discrepancy between his reading level and his intellectual potential as measured by standardized tests. Quantitative evaluation is always used with caution because test scores alone do not provide accurate appraisal of a process as complex as reading. Reading difficulties occurs among many learners as a result of various causes, such as, lack of foundational and pre-reading skills, contextual disadvantages, such as poverty with learners not being exposed to books and reading from an early age and ineffective teaching methods (Dedan, 2011).

According to Snowling and Hulme (2012), define reading difficulties as a significant barrier to academic success and personal development in children. This challenges often extend beyond the classroom, affecting a child's self-esteem, motivation, and social interactions. As a result, schools play a critical role not only in academic instruction but also in providing emotional and psychological support through structured counseling strategies. School-based counseling offers targeted interventions that address both the academic and emotional needs of children with reading difficulties, fostering resilience, confidence, and adaptive learning behaviors.

School-based counseling strategies provides ways to address the academic, emotional, and behavioral needs of children with reading difficulties. Reading difficulties, often classified under specific learning difficulties, hinder students' ability to decode, comprehend, and engage with written texts. These challenges frequently lead to academic underachievement and emotional distress such as low self-esteem, anxiety, and frustration. School-based counseling is component of the educational system that focuses on the psychological, emotional, and social development of students. It provides accessible mental health support within the school environment and plays a critical role in academic achievement, behavioral development. According to the American School Counselor Association (ASCA), school counselors help students in the domains of academic development, career planning, and personal/social growth (ASCA, 2019).

The school counselors within schools serve as key figures in identifying struggling readers and providing targeted support through both direct intervention and collaboration with teachers and parents. School counselors can offer individualized or small-group sessions to help students develop coping strategies, build self-confidence, and maintain motivation in the face of learning difficulties (Milsom & Glanville, 2010).

Furthermore, effective school-based counseling strategies supports inclusion by working closely with special education teams to design individualized education programs (IEPs), advocate for necessary accommodations, and monitor students' progress. Studies have shown that when school counselors are actively engaged in supporting students with reading difficulties, the students demonstrate improvements not only in academic performance but also in overall school engagement (Nelson & Harwood, 2011).

In the Nigerian educational system, the effectiveness of school-based counseling strategies is becoming increasingly recognized. These strategies not only enhance reading competence but also contribute to improving students' motivation, classroom participation, and academic outcomes.

School-Based Counseling Strategies

School-based counseling strategies refer to planned, structured, and goal-oriented interventions designed within the school environment to address the academic, emotional, social, and behavioral needs of students. These strategies are implemented by school counselors, teachers, special educators and psychologists to help learners overcome challenges that may hinder their academic performance and personal development.

According to Erford (2015), school-based counseling strategies are systematic approaches used within the school setting to promote students' well-being, improve learning outcomes, and foster positive behavior. They involve preventive, remedial, and developmental techniques such as individual counseling, group counseling, peer mentoring, career guidance, and behavior modification programs.

Adediran (2019) describes school-based counseling as a mechanism through which schools provide supportive services that guide students in making appropriate academic and personal decisions. Such strategies not only help in addressing immediate concerns like poor study habits or test anxiety but also build long-term resilience, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills. School-based counseling strategies have become an integral part of educational systems, particularly in promoting students' social, emotional, and academic development. Counseling within the school environment provides timely intervention for students facing academic difficulties, behavioral challenges, and personal issues.

Okobiah and Okorodudu (2014) assert that counseling strategies such as problem-solving skills training, cognitive restructuring, and life-skill education significantly enhance students' resilience and capacity to cope with academic pressures. Similarly, Egbochuku (2008) emphasized that effective counseling services within schools not only enhance students' adjustment but also foster a positive learning environment. A study by Akinsola (2019), revealed that school-based counseling strategies like study skills workshops, career orientation, and behavioral modification techniques have been instrumental in addressing academic underachievement among secondary school students. These strategies enable counselors to intervene early in students' academic and emotional problems, thereby reducing school dropouts and improving performance.

According to Egbo (2015), school-based counseling strategies is an integral part of the educational process aimed at assisting learners to understand themselves, adjust effectively to school life, and achieve their full potential. Similarly, American School Counselor Association (ASCA, 2019) emphasizes that school counseling programs are comprehensive in scope, preventive in design, and developmental in nature, providing academic, career, and social-emotional support for all students.

School-based counseling strategies provides targeted psychological and academic interventions within the school setting, ensuring accessibility and early identification of students at risk. Counselors work collaboratively with teachers, parents, and special education professionals to create individualized support plans, offer remedial strategies, and foster a safe environment where students feel encouraged to improve (Milsom, 2006).

In addition, UNESCO (2017) highlighted the global recognition of school-based counseling as a vital approach to supporting learners with diverse needs, particularly in low-resource contexts. Counseling strategies that emphasize collaboration among teachers, parents, and school counselors provide a holistic framework for addressing students' challenges.

Counseling Strategies in Supporting Children with Reading Difficulties

The integration of counseling into the broader educational framework promotes a holistic approach to learning, where the emotional and psychological needs of children with reading difficulties are addressed alongside their academic needs. Thus, school-based counseling is a vital component of

comprehensive support systems that foster both academic success and personal development for learners with reading difficulties.

Counseling strategies such as individual or group therapy, assistive technology, cognitive-behavioral interventions, and collaboration with special education teachers help identify learning barriers, enhance coping skills, and develop personalized educational plans. Through these integrated support systems, school counselors work closely with teachers, parents, and other professionals to ensure that students with reading difficulties receive comprehensive assistance tailored to their unique needs (Macklem, 2011). However, early identification and intervention through school-based counseling strategies have been shown to significantly improve outcomes for students with reading difficulties.

Educational Application for school-Based Counselling Strategies to Children with Reading Difficulties

The educational application can be seen in the following ways:

i. Individualized Learning Plan

Counsellors can collaborate with parents and other professionals to design home-based learning tasks tailored to the child's strengths and weaknesses. Activities like storytelling, word games, and role-play make reading fun and personalized (Hallahan, Kauffman & Pullen, 2015). An individualized learning plan is a personalized educational roadmap designed to meet the unique learning needs of children with reading difficulties. Learners with reading disability often struggle with phonological processing, decoding, spelling, and fluency, making reading a major challenge (Snowling & Hulme, 2012). An individualized learning plan provides targeted interventions that address these specific difficulties while leveraging the child's strengths. Teacher begins by identifying the child's reading strengths and weaknesses through standardized reading assessments and teacher observations. The areas to assess are phonemic awareness, decoding, word recognition, and comprehension etc. For example, if the child struggles with decoding but shows strong comprehension when listening, the individualized learning plan should emphasize phonics while supporting comprehension through oral activities.

ii. Assistive Technology to Aid Reading

Assistive Technology provides students with reading difficulties tools that support their literacy development, enhance comprehension, and foster independence in learning. The goal is not just to compensate for the disability, but also to remediate reading problems by providing access, practice, and reinforcement (Elkind, Cohen, & Murray, 1993). For instance, text-to-speech programs read digital or scanned text aloud, which helps students who struggle with word recognition or fluency to focus more on comprehension. Similarly, audiobooks provide alternative ways of accessing literature. According to Al-Azawei, Parslow, and Lundqvist (2016), the integration of assistive technology in education enhances inclusive learning by meeting the diverse needs of students with difficulties, enabling them to participate equally with their peers.

iii. Emotional and Psychological Support

School counselors and teachers can provide one-on-one emotional support to help children express frustrations about reading. Counseling also helps address negative self-concepts and provides coping strategies (Adeyemo, 2011). Emotional and psychological support emphasize empathy, encouragement, and positive reinforcement. This reduces anxiety and builds self-confidence, which is essential for children who often struggle with self-esteem due to their reading challenges (Lerner & Johns, 2015). Children with reading difficulties often struggle with low self-esteem and frustration. School-based counselling strategies such as positive reinforcement, encouragement, and stress management techniques help to create a safe emotional climate.

School-based counseling can incorporate technology, such as audiobooks, speech-to-text software, and

interactive reading apps, to make learning engaging. This strategy supports children with reading difficulties by compensating for decoding challenges.

Reading Difficulties

Reading disability, often referred to as dyslexia, is a specific learning disorder that affects an individual's ability to read, decode, comprehend, and interpret written language, despite having average or above-average intelligence and adequate educational opportunities. Children with reading difficulties experience persistent difficulties in recognizing words accurately, spelling, and fluency, which in turn hinders their overall academic performance.

According to the American Psychiatric Association (APA, 2013) in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5), reading disability is categorized under Specific Learning Disorders and is characterized by significant and persistent difficulties in reading skills that are substantially below what is expected for a child's age and grade level. An individual with reading disability demonstrates difficulties in reading skills that are unexpected in relation to age, cognitive ability, quantity and quality of instruction, and intervention. The reading difficulties are not the result of generalized developmental delay or sensory impairment (Lundberg and Høien, 2001; Matter and Goldstein, 2001). Reading disability may be characterized by difficulties in single word reading, initial difficulties decoding or sounding out words, difficulties reading sight words and insufficient phonological processing.

In educational contexts, reading difficulties manifest in forms such as; difficulty in decoding words, slow and effortful reading, poor spelling and writing skills and challenges in comprehension despite adequate oral language skills.

Factors Responsible for Reading Difficulties

The factors responsible for reading difficulties are many, some which are as follows:

i. Neurological Factors

Reading difficulties such as dyslexia are often linked to brain differences in processing language and phonological awareness. Neuroimaging studies show that individuals with reading difficulties have difficulties in areas of the brain responsible for decoding words and phonemes (Shaywitz & Shaywitz, 2008). Research shows that optimal brain development is essential for effective learning. Conditions such as brain injuries, epilepsy, or developmental disorders like dyslexia, ADHD, and autism spectrum disorders can disrupt normal neurological functioning and, in turn, affect students' capacity to process information, maintain concentration, and retain knowledge (American Psychiatric Association, 2013).

ii. Genetic and Hereditary Factors

Genetic and hereditary factors refer to the biological traits and characteristics that are passed from parents to their offspring through genes. These factors play a critical role in shaping an individual's physical, cognitive, and psychological development. According to Plomin, DeFries, Knopik and Neiderhiser (2016), heredity contributes significantly to variations in intelligence, personality, and even susceptibility to certain health conditions. For instance, a child may inherit talents, aptitudes, or learning difficulties from their parents. Researches indicate that reading difficulties can run in families. Children with a family history of dyslexia or other learning difficulties are at a higher risk of developing similar challenges (Olson, Keenan, Byrne, & Samuelsson, 2014).

iii. Environmental Factors

Environmental factors refer to the external conditions and surroundings that influence an individual's growth, development, and performance. In the context of education, these factors include the physical,

social, and cultural environments in which students live and learn. A child's home environment, exposure to books, parental involvement in early literacy activities, and socioeconomic background can significantly influence reading development. Poor stimulation at home may increase the risk of reading difficulties (Evans, Kelley, & Sikora, 2014).

iv. Instructional Factors

This refers to the various elements within the teaching and learning process that influence how effectively students acquire knowledge and skills. These factors include teaching methods, instructional materials, classroom management, teacher-student interaction, assessment strategies, and the overall quality of lesson delivery. Inadequate or inappropriate teaching strategies, overcrowded classrooms, and lack of early intervention may contribute to persistent reading difficulties (Torgesen, 2002).

v. Emotional and Psychological Factors

Emotional and psychological is one the factor plays crucial role in shaping students' academic performance and overall adjustment in school. Emotions such as anxiety, motivation, self-esteem, and stress can either enhance or hinder learning. For instance, low self-esteem, anxiety, and lack of motivation may not directly cause reading difficulties but can worsen reading difficulties by reducing engagement and persistence (Marsh & Craven, 2006).

Conclusion

In conclusion, school-based counseling strategies help in providing educational support for children with reading difficulties in Nigeria. Their effectiveness is further enhanced when complemented by school-based counseling approaches, creating a more holistic support system. The use of individualized educational plans, alongside emotional and psychological support, as well as the integration of assistive technology, offers a comprehensive framework for helping children overcome reading challenges and improve their academic outcomes.

Suggestions

1. The school counselors should employ both educational application such as assistive technology and individualized counseling for children with reading difficulties to support, motivation, and build confidence for them.
2. Workshops and in-service training should be organized for school counselors and teachers on modern counseling strategies and remedial techniques to help children overcome reading difficulties.
3. Teachers, counselors and special educators should collaborate more closely, integrating counseling strategies into classroom activities to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment for children with reading difficulties.

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